

The charter is the foundational document that describes the rationale, goals, plan of work, resources needed, terms and conditions, and outcomes of a Center for Digital Humanities at Princeton (hereafter CDH) project. Charters are written by core members of a project team in a series of planning meetings taking place over the course of a month. The planning process is intensive, collaborative, and requires substantial input from everyone on a team. Charters serve as formalized agreements among all team members on such crucial questions as scope, technical design, infrastructural needs, and success criteria.

This is a digital copy of a “living document” at a single point in time. Charters are amended as necessary throughout the project lifecycle to document major changes and serve as part of the CDH project archive. CDH charters and their planning documents exist in several forms as we have refined them over the years and tailored them to the several types of projects we have supported. For more about CDH project management, including the charter process, visit: <https://cdh.princeton.edu/research/project-management>.

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Simulating risk, risking simulations Project Charter

2022-2023 CDH Research Partnership

Agreed on by Lara Buchak and Rebecca Sutton Koeser on July 19, 2022.

Updated April 2023 with expanded project team and revised timeline.

Updated May 2023 to revise project team roles and delete work plan and resource list.

Project Overview

1. Project abstract and justification.

Computational philosophy has a long history, and yet is not typically considered as falling under the “big tent” of digital humanities. Computational models and methodologies have enabled work in philosophy that would not otherwise be possible, but this research is not data-driven like most digital humanities work. In this project, we will work with computer simulations of agent-based modeling to explore the implications of incorporating a variety of risk attitudes (risk avoidance and risk seeking) into game theoretic interactions. The work will involve revising existing simulations¹ and developing new ones to incorporate Buchak’s theory of risk and rationality² in the context of group dynamics. Since Buchak’s theory has previously been applied only to individual decision-making, this will be a significant advance in the philosophical literature.

We will build, run, analyze, and interpret a variety of simulations in order to determine whether incorporating risk attitudes into existing simulations impacts results from previous models of rationality, and will also explore the impact of risk attitudes in other scenarios. But we will also consider critically the approach of working with and interpreting simplified models and stochastic simulations abstracted in code in the larger context of current digital humanities work, putting it in conversation with work with and criticism of computational models of language and other models of humanistic knowledge.

¹ Brian Skyrms, *The Stag Hunt and the Evolution of Social Structure* (Cambridge, UK ; New York: Cambridge University Press, 2004).

² Lara Buchak, *Risk and Rationality* (Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press, 2017).

2. Scope statement.

- Adapt existing simulations to incorporate risk weights and determine how this impacts the conclusions from the original simulation
- Develop new simulations to test risk-weighted behavior in group interactions
- Co-author a ~9,000 word scholarly article reporting on results for publication in a philosophy journal
 - A full article draft to be completed during the grant period; expect to revise and submit for publication after the grant
- Co-author a ~5,000 word DH-focused article about modeling and simulations that puts the computational work of this project in conversation with other DH modeling, abstraction, interpretation of simulations, etc (e.g., current conversations about large language models)
 - Potentially publish in Startwords with interactive elements to demonstrate approach/simulation/models

4. Out of scope.

- Installations, explorable explainers, public humanities outputs

3. Deliverables and Milestones Dates.

April 19, 2023: begin project work

July 31: simulations complete, or far enough along to begin drafting articles

October 31: complete first draft of both articles

4. Audience.

- Philosophers and game theorists
- Digital Humanities community
- Literate public interested in philosophy, game theory, models & simulation, etc

5. Project team.

Team members

Co-PI: Lara Buchak

Co-PI: Rebecca Sutton Koeser

Project Manager: Mary Naydan

Project advisors

Natalia Ermolaev

Ryan Heuser

David Kinney

Philosophy grad students may be recruited for input and brainstorming; may help with interpreting simulations, suggesting additional games to test in simulations, refining simulations, etc. Any students who become sufficiently involved will be considered project team members.

6. Budget.

[Project budget available on request.]

7. Risks or interdependencies.

- Revised simulations may not have any interesting results (i.e., incorporating risk doesn't change the outcome at all)

8. Rights and permissions.

- Not working with any data that is confidential, sensitive, personal, or includes any identifying information.
- Code written for the simulations will be made available on GitHub under an Apache 2.0 license and deposited in Zenodo.
- Plan to publish articles as open access; this will require paying an open access fee for the philosophy article.

9. Post-grant plans for project.

- Finish revising philosophy article and submit for publication (Buchak leads)
- Finish revising DH article and submit for publication (Koeser leads)
- Invite respondents for a workshop or panel to discuss the results from the work
- Present results at relevant conferences/workshops